

Integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) In Plant Sciences- A Review of AI Assisted Techniques Used for The Advancement of Plant Sciences

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Abstract:

Artificial Intelligence is a powerful, innovative, advanced and valuable tool that enables machines to perform operations or tasks in a versatile manner associated with human intelligence. Plant Sciences or Botany is one important branch of Pure Sciences that has witnessed many revolutionary changes by integrating, adapting and executing major novice scientific inventions, techniques and discoveries. The present review focuses upon the interdisciplinary and multifaceted approach of AI in Plant Sciences that has been associated with diverse areas like Agricultural Sciences, Plant Breeding, Disease management, increased productivity, species discovery, plant evolution, and ecological research. Moreover the accuracy that AI offers by incorporating machine learning algorithms, neural networks and big data analytic tools is unprecedented. However, challenges and ethical considerations in this field highlight the need for consistent research and adoption of standard guidelines to utilise this technology in a safe and secure manner for the holistic development of human race without disturbing the harmony between man, machine and the environment.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence (AI), Interdisciplinary, Agricultural Sciences, Plant Breeding, Disease Management, Increased Productivity, Species Discovery, Plant Evolution, Ecological Research, Pure Sciences*

Introduction:

Humans are considered to be one of the oldest members to inhabit Planet Earth. These dominant species have been successful to keep a strong foothold because of an inherent quality that nature has endowed them with. This remarkable and astonishing feature which makes humans stand out amongst other living organisms is – human intelligence arising from their capacity to think in a cognitive manner. Human intelligence can be defined as the capacity of human beings to understand, reason, enquire, plan and execute actions in a logical manner.

This unparalleled human intelligence has given rise to a major technological revolution known as Artificial Intelligence (AI). AI can be defined as the ability of machines or a system to think in a way that simulates human intelligence^[6]. The beauty of AI lies in the fact that it is a technique that closely imitates human cognitive skills like

learning, analysis, memory, perception, etc. One of the greatest innovators in the field of AI was John McCarthy, who is widely recognized as the father of Artificial Intelligence due to his astounding contribution in the field of Computer Science and AI. He introduced and defined AI at a conference on the campus of Dartmouth College; which was later formalized as a scientific discipline, proposing that machines could simulate any aspect of learning or intelligence. It was in the mid-1950s that McCarthy coined the term “Artificial Intelligence” which he would define as “**the science and engineering of making intelligent machines**”^[6]. “The Turing Test” is another important milestone in the field of AI that was proposed by Alan Turing in 1950. This test exhibits a method to demonstrate the extent to which human intelligence can be simulated by a machine.^[1, 4]

This dynamic field has proved to be of utmost use to various domains like Mathematics,

Material Science, Physics, Chemistry, Medicinal Sciences, Life Sciences, Geo science, etc. Plant Science is one of the important components of environment management and sustainable development. Recent advancements in science and technology have transformed the conventional approaches in plant sciences pertaining to different areas like crop yield, early disease detection, climate analysis, species identification, soil parameter analysis and ecological studies. The present paper aims to highlight the avenues of utilization, limitations and ethical considerations relating to this emergent technology that has the capacity to simulate human intelligence.

Figure 1: Applications of AI in plant sciences.

Big Data Analysis:

Big Data analysis involves the integration of vast datasets of information pertaining to agricultural practices like irrigation, fertigation, application of pesticides, drought, infestation etc., in order to optimize yield and generate minimum wastage. Arable and Crop X are examples of crop-intelligence companies that are working towards practices like smart irrigation, adoption of sensors for accurate weather and soil analysis and thereby helping farmers.

Block Chain Technology:

This system is a shared digital ledger that securely records transactions across a network of computers known as nodes. Information is a sensitive tool that needs to be handled in a secure manner. Block chain Technology provides a secure

and immutable platform for storing, sharing and verifying data that can help combat counterfeit seeds or plants by integrating a tamper-proof record of their originality. This is especially important in experiments involving plant breeding programs where maintaining the integrity of genetic variants is of utmost importance for the successful establishment of any individual and precision irrigation systems as exhibited by Arable and Crop X that promote sustainable practices.

Internet Of Things (IoT):

This avenue of AI includes sensors installed on-field that collect real-time information and transmit the same to a centralized system where AI algorithms perform analysis to arrive at logical decisions. These are important in environmental monitoring as physical, chemical and biological parameters like temperature, humidity, light intensity, mineral nutrients, pathogens infection [4], etc., can be easily monitored. Also, this helps in early disease detection and efficient crop management of agricultural lands.

Visual (Image Capture and Analysis) Techniques:

AI integrated with high-end imaging techniques like digital cameras, hyper-spectral imaging or 3 D scanners help in capturing real-time visual data of biological importance. This is used in analysis of Plant Phenotype [10], disease management, crop yield prediction and management based on data sets like plant density, canopy cover, fruit count, etc. AI driven automated weed-control systems adopt machine learning and computer vision to accurately identify weeds in crop fields. For example Blue River technology has developed ‘See and Spray’ technology for this purpose which has exhibited up to 90% less usage of herbicide application [5]. In a study published in MDPI, a deep-learning based method [9] was used to identify wheat yellow rust from unmanned aerial vehicle with 98% accuracy thereby enabling timely control measures to reduce economic losses [9, 10].

Figure 2 AI, sensors and robotics based dynamic 3-D plant phenotyping and precision agriculture framework.

Artificial Neural Network (ANN):

ANN is an integrated network of nodes (artificial neurons) that is inspired by the structure and function of human brain's interconnected neurons. This system is used in crop management as it helps in early disease detection by analyzing preliminary plant symptoms (during initial stages of disease-cycle). This is an important feature that helps to optimize crop production as chances of crop failure due to pathogens can be minimized due to accurate diagnostic methods. Also, gene expression analysis is another arena that has largely reaped the benefits of this technology due to identification of relationships between genes and their functions. This helps to accurately identify and analyze the relationship between factors like light, temperature, nutrient availability, leaf area, biomass accumulation and root development. For example, a study published in the journal *Computer and Electronics in Agriculture* demonstrated an AI system's capability to detect apple scab with 95% accuracy in identifying disease pattern. [7, 10, 11]

Robotics:

A Robot is a mechanical device that is programmed to perform tasks autonomously or semi-autonomously. With reference to plant sciences, robots can be installed on agricultural lands to conduct experiments and perform specific tasks that enables minimal mechanical input on field and accurate real-time analysis of data pertaining to

plant growth, environmental conditions, precision agriculture [3, 5, 7], crop protection etc.

Challenges in Utilizing AI:

AI is hugely reliant on data therefore, data privacy and security concerns prevail over the utilization of AI on a large scale. Cyber security attacks are common modes via which data can be extracted and put to misuse against national interest. To deal with such exigencies presence of a strong regulatory system is of utmost importance. Also, automation is a potent threat to the generation of employment opportunities leading to displacement of jobs. In due process of automation the onus of accountability and liability is lost as there is no specific bearer of the terms of use. Training AI models is a tedious task and it also relies upon excessive energy utilization that has environmental consequences associated with it. Rampant spread of misinformation and malicious usage of data is another challenging domain of AI as it can disrupt the democratic nature of the society. Moreover, in a developing country like India, the exuberant costs of handling complex data sets involved in AI in a secure manner is a matter of serious consideration.

Ethical Considerations:

AI is an integration of different domains created for the betterment of human civilization. However, unlike human intelligence, AI focusses on data-driven models to arrive at logical conclusions. Here, the role of ethics or interpretation of right/wrong comes into picture. As machines can be structurally designed to perform operations accurately within a short span of time but, simulating the capabilities of human brain cells to solve any complex task with a multi-dimensional approach is not within the defined boundaries of AI.

Conclusion:

Development of AI as a tool to assist progress of the society is one of the foundation pillars for the creation of this multi-faceted technology. Adoption of these techniques requires a

collaborative and ethical approach. Ensuring integrity and privacy of data while focusing upon the progress of mankind has to be met with a cautious balance. Above-all it is imperative to maintain the human nature of decisions while attempting to address issues of mankind. In conclusion, informed utilization of Natural Intelligence (NI) is necessary for effective implantation of Artificial Intelligence (AI).

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